

IUC 01: Web-based demonstration and teaching framework for MSE research data infrastructure

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One of the key objectives of NFDI-MatWerk is to disseminate its latest developments in digitalisation and data science to current and future generations of scientists and professionals, as well as to raise awareness of the importance and benefits of implementing an appropriate data research management strategy. This encompasses important education and training aspects. This will be achieved, amongst other things, through the creation of collaborative platforms, a large number of interactive workshops and annual conferences.

To achieve this objective, the IUC01 is collaborating with the network of experts at NFDI-MatWerk to create new training and teaching opportunities for young researchers. One of the main activities is the organisation of workshops, which serve not only to train young scientists but also to receive feedback on the needs of the MSE community in order to further develop the training offers. In this context, four summer/winter schools were organised in Saarbrücken and Dresden. The inaugural school was designed to facilitate interaction between researchers already engaged in RDM (primarily within NFDI-MatWerk) and international students, researchers, and professionals with limited familiarity with this topic. This was accomplished in the frame of an EUSMAT¹ Alumni Meeting at Saarland University. Feedback highlighted the need for balancing theoretical lectures with practical sessions, incorporating collaborative tasks, and providing more detailed overviews of the training content beforehand to better prepare participants. The evaluation proved invaluable in gauging the necessity for sensitizing the community and identifying the most pertinent content to be provided. This task was greatly enhanced by the interviews conducted by the Fraunhofer Institute for Material and Beam technology (Fraunhofer IWS, Dresden) with numerous MSE researchers in Germany.

¹ <https://eusmat.net>

Two short educational programmes were offered during the summer and winter terms, respectively, at Saarbrücken and Dresden. These were designed for doctoral students and postdoctoral researchers. The contents included modules on metadata, research management plans, electronic lab notebooks (ELNs), and Python programming, as well as some practical examples of application of RDM in the field of MSE. From the evaluation (see Figure 1), it is evident that the topics, especially Fundamentals of Scientific Metadata and Data Management Plan, are highly relevant. Participants recommended incorporating more concrete examples and hands-on exercises for Python and ELNs to enhance practical understanding. Additionally, suggestions were made to follow the process in real-time during sessions and provide pre-session instructions for necessary software installations.

Fig. 1: Evaluation of the Summer School 2023 regarding relevance of the different contents.

A further spring school with similar content was dedicated to international master students in the EUSMAT AMASE programme. It became evident that the majority of students were not aware of FAIR principles and RDM, and they found it however very relevant (Figure 2).

Based on feedback from the NFDI Spring School held in Saarbrücken, participants recommended several enhancements for future sessions:

- **Practical Focus:** Increase the number of hands-on exercises and real-world application tasks, particularly for Python and ELN sessions.
- **Detailed Preparation:** Provide advance notice for necessary software installations and offer detailed overviews of training content beforehand.
- **Balance Content:** Balance theoretical lectures with practical sessions and collaborative tasks to maintain engagement and facilitate understanding.

Topic Relevance: Emphasize topics like metadata management and ELNs, incorporating FAIR principles and basic programming skills, which participants found highly relevant for their research and career development.

Fig. 2: Evaluation of the Spring School 2024 regarding relevance of the different contents.

The conclusion was that implementing such training at the master level and to some extent at the bachelor level would be highly beneficial (Figure 3).

Fig. 3: Evaluation of the Spring School 2024 regarding career time which the contents of RDM should be taught.

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